

IgG-mediated food intolerances – prevalence, mechanisms, and cross-reactivities among the Bulgarian population. Contemporary aspects

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Abstract

Background: The prevalence of food intolerances (FIs) in 1679 individuals over 18 years of age from Bulgaria and some cross-reactivities between the intolerances to different foods were studied.

Method: A blood test was used: *Food Detective* – CNS (Cambridge Nutrition Sciences Ltd.) to identify the foodstuffs to which the body exhibits intolerance. The basis of the study is the formation of antibodies of class IgG, which are markers for intolerance to different food groups and food products. Individuals were tested for 46 foods.

Results: The most common food intolerances are to cereals (60–90% of the subjects), probably related to the high consumption of such products in Bulgaria; to milk and eggs (about 50–68%); legumes (about 24–43%) and nuts (24–40%); and fish and shellfish (about 12–25%). Gluten intolerance is shown by 41.2% of the subjects. Intolerance to vegetables, fruits, and meat has the lowest relative share in the study. Significant correlations were found for 20 pairs of foods, with a high degree of correlation between simultaneous intolerance to soy, tomatoes, and legumes; peppers and mushrooms; and eggs with peppers, mushrooms, and tomatoes.

Conclusion: Specific features of the Bulgarian population in the prevalence of food intolerances and the correlations between them have been identified, contributing to the prevention and treatment of nutritional diseases, overweight, and other eating disorders; optimization of dietary regimens at the individual level; prescription of healthy individual diets; and maintenance of individual health.

Keywords

food intolerance, IgG antibodies, immunological reactions, food allergies

Introduction

Food intolerances (FI) are widespread worldwide, including in Bulgaria. According to various authors, they affect from 5–7 to 20% (Gaur and Kumar 2013) of the population, and their actual prevalence is probably higher, but there are no

studies in this direction in Bulgaria. Adverse food reactions are usually classified as food allergy and food intolerance (Zeng 2013; Cruchet and Verbeke 2022) and include immunomediated food allergies and non-immunomediated intolerances, whose pathogenetic mechanisms are different but are nevertheless often confused (Gargano et al. 2021).

The term **food intolerance** has been used non-specifically to define a wide range of disorders related to food intake. Recently, the use of the term “*non-immunological adverse reactions to foods*” was recommended as a more correct clinical definition (Colella and Salvador Parisi 2023). As an immunological identification, food allergy is most often mediated by IgE antibodies, and food intolerance is associated with IgG class antibodies (Beyer and Teuber 2005; Gaur and Kumar 2013). The intestinal wall is directly involved in these adverse reactions to some foods, since it plays a key role in food absorption and in the regulation of the immune system. Enzyme deficiency and reactions resembling chronic food intoxication are often present.

IgG-mediated food intolerance is associated with a wide range of specific and non-specific symptoms – allergies (rash, hives, and asthma), gastrointestinal symptoms, and irritable bowel syndrome. Possible manifestations include drowsiness after eating, migraine-like headache, increased irritability, bloating, a feeling of heaviness in the stomach, diarrhea, constipation, heartburn, vomiting, muscle and joint pain, sneezing, rashes, lethargy, and a general feeling of being unwell, as well as many others, alone or in combination with several symptoms (Collard 2010; Guo et al. 2012; Kumar et al. 2013). In individuals with food intolerance, allergic manifestations are possible, and in individuals with allergic symptoms, IgG antibodies to certain foods are detected instead of IgE antibodies characteristic of food allergies (Shakoor et al. 2016), which makes food intolerances and food allergies sometimes difficult to differentiate.

The aim of this study is to examine the prevalence of food intolerances among the population in Bulgaria, their distribution by gender and by groups and types of foods (products), as well as the available correlations between individual food intolerances.

Materials and methods

Objectives

The study is establishing the frequency (prevalence, distribution) of food intolerance for persons over 18 years of age from Bulgaria and some cross-reactivities between the intolerances to various foods. The data are from a study on the incidence and prevalence of food intolerance for 46 major food types (listed in Table 1).

A total of 1679 people were surveyed who consulted a nutritionist for advice and/or prescribing a proper diet. They all visited the dietitian's office at will. Average age of the subjects surveyed – 41.6 years.

In this paper are discussed food intolerances, evaluating their scientific reliability and focusing on IgG analysis-based immunoenzymatic tests, which are the most relevant tests for intolerance diagnosis (Palmieri et al. 2011).

Method

A blood test is used: **Food Detective** – CNS (Cambridge Nutrition Sciences Ltd.) to identify the foodstuffs to which

the body exhibits intolerance. The basis of the study is the forming of antibodies of class IgG, markers for intolerance to different food groups (and food products) (Table 1). The study is based on IgG class antibodies that are emerging as markers of intolerance to different food groups and types.

Microarray for food-specific IgG antibodies

Food-specific IgG antibodies were detected using a microarray test (Genarrayt, Omega Diagnostics Group, Scotland, United Kingdom – <https://senecapartners.co.uk/portfolio/omega-diagnostics-group-plc/>), which measures IgG levels against 46 food substances using a single blood sample. This microarray testing procedure involved incubation of the patient serum sample for 30 minutes at room temperature on a glass microscope slide containing a microarray of 223 food extracts.

After this primary incubation, the slide was washed to remove unbound proteins. Following this, anti-human IgG conjugated to horseradish peroxidase was added to the slide and incubated for another 30 minutes at room temperature. The slide was washed again to remove the unbound conjugate. After washing, 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) substrate was added to detect specific antibody binding. A third incubation was performed for 10 minutes, and then the slide was washed with distilled water. Finally, the slides were centrifuged and scanned by a high-resolution flatbed scanner associated with computer software that interprets the optical densities of the samples. IgG levels less than 30 U/mL were considered negative, whereas levels either equal to or more than 30 U/mL were considered positive. Values of food-specific IgG antibodies either equal to or more than 30 U/mL were included in the study.

The test is performed by taking a blood sample from the test person's finger. Different types of nutritional extracts are used to identify foods to which antibodies are produced (foods that induce the production of antibodies in a particular blood sample). The test is safe and informative for the presence of intolerance to appropriate foods. Intolerance is classified into three degrees: *light, medium, and heavy*, depending on its manifestations.

Individuals were tested for 46 foods shown in Table 1.

Statistical methods

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Software version 21 (New York, USA statistical package). Variation, correlation analysis, and cross tables were used.

The **chi-square test** was used for comparison of proportions. Test $\times 2$ (chi-squared) – for studying correlation-type relationships. In this study, it was analyzed to what extent a supposed dependence (or some other type of relationship) exists objectively, non-randomly, and manifests itself as such among a studied set of units. Reliability at $p < 0.01$; $p < 0.05$.

Fisher's test – Fisher's F-criterion (one-way analysis of variance), for comparing the distribution of two or more variables, allows for an accurate calculation of the significance of the deviation from the null hypothesis (p-value). A p-value < 0.5 (< 0.001) was considered statistically significant.

Table 1. List of foods used in the study.

1. Oats	13. Milk	25. Carrots	36. Cocoa
2. Wheat	14. Eggs	26. Leek	37. Apple
3. Rice	15. Chicken meat	27. Potatoes	38. Currant
4. Corn	16. Lamb meat	28. Celery	39. Olives
5. Rye	17. Veal meat	29. Cucumber	40. Oranges and lemons
6. Grain / paste, c. /	18. Pork meat	30. Peppers – red, green, yellow	41. Strawberries
7. Gluten	19. White fish – cod, flounder	31. beans – peas, lentils, beans	42. Tomatoes
8. Almonds	20. Freshwater fish – salmon, trout	32. Grapefruit	43. Ginger
9. Brazil nuts	21. Tuna	33. Melon and watermelon	44. Garlic
10. Cashew	22. Shellfish – shrimps, crabs, lobsters, mussels	34. Peanuts	45. Mushroom
11. Tea	23. Broccoli	35. Soya	46. Yeast
12. Walnuts	24. White cabbage		

Likelihood ratios (LR) (descriptive statistics) were used to assess the probability that individuals who have a food intolerance to a given food will also have (show) an intolerance to another food. Pairs of foods from the 46 types considered were compared. LR values > 1 indicate a positive relationship between the analyzed foods, respectively: 1–2 – minimal (very weak), 2–5 – weak (low), 5–10 – medium/moderate, and over 10 – strong (high) dependence. In negative LR values, the sought relationship is not present.

Results

The data from Table 2 show the following distribution of the frequency of food intolerances:

- **Cereals, gluten, yeast:** The most common intolerances are to cereals and flours, respectively: wheat – 92.8%, corn – 69.9%, rye flour – 63.9%, and grain – 54.5%. Intolerance to gluten was found in 41.2% and to yeast in 61.1% of the subjects studied.
- **Milk and eggs:** About half of the subjects studied (51.7%) showed intolerance to milk, and even more often (in 68.3% of all subjects) there was intolerance to eggs.
- **Meat:** This intolerance is significantly less common compared to intolerance to cereals, gluten, milk, and eggs. The most common intolerance is to pork – 2.3%, followed by that to chicken – 1.6%, to lamb – 1.4%, and the rarest is to beef – 0.9% of the surveyed individuals.
- **Legumes, soy:** The data show intolerance to peas, lentils, and beans in 31.5% of the individuals in the study; to rice, in 43.2%; and to soy, in 24.1%.
- **Fish and shellfish:** The most common intolerance is to shellfish (crabs, mussels, etc.) – 25.5%, followed by that to white fish – 12.4%, freshwater fish (mix) – 6.5%, and the rarest intolerance is to tuna – in only 2.3%.
- **Vegetables, fruits, and nuts:**
 - ◊ Vegetables – the most common intolerance is to peppers (22.5%), followed by potatoes (19.0%), celery (14.2%), carrots (12.3%), tomatoes (11.7%), mushrooms (10.4%), leeks (6.6%),

and garlic (2.0%), and the rarest to olives (0.8%), broccoli (0.5%), and cucumbers (0.3%).

- ◊ Fruits – the leading place is occupied by intolerance to oranges and lemons (13.2%) and strawberries (8.7%); significantly rarer are intolerances to grapefruit (3.8%), blueberries (1.1%), melon and watermelon (1.0%), and apple (0.5%).
- ◊ Nuts over 30% of all surveyed individuals have one or more intolerances to nuts. The most common is intolerance to cashews (39.9%), followed by almonds and peanuts (35.7% and 34.9%), Brazil nuts (24.4%), and walnuts are best tolerated (7.5% of those surveyed have such an intolerance).
- **Other products – cocoa, tea, and ginger:** The most common is intolerance to cocoa – found in 11.8%; to ginger – in 3.7%; and to tea – very rare at 0.8%.

By food group, the highest prevalence is intolerance to cereals (between 60 and 90% of the surveyed individuals), followed by intolerance to milk and eggs (about 50–68%), which are proven allergenic foods. The third place is occupied by legumes (about 24–43%) and nuts (24–40%), followed by intolerances to fish and shellfish (about 12–25%). Intolerances to vegetables, fruits, and meat have the lowest relative share in the study.

The comparison by gender shows that significant differences are present in:

- **Wheat:** with LR = 11.26, $p < 0.01$ —high level of significance
- **Leek:** LR = 3.35, $p < 0.02$ —low level of significance
- **Cocoa:** LR = 11.14, $p < 0.02$ —high level of significance
- **Mushrooms:** LR = 3.23, $p < 0.03$ —low level of significance

Table 3 presents the food intolerances in the studied individuals by degree of manifestation. The degrees of manifestation are, respectively, **light, medium, and heavy**.

The data show that the foods with the most “heavy” degree of manifestation of food intolerance are eggs (11.2%) and milk (8.7%), followed by wheat (7.6%), yeast (4.8%), corn (3.5%), and cashews (3.3%). They emerge as foods with the highest potential to cause “heavy” intolerances. This po-

Table 2. Prevalence of food intolerances among the surveyed individuals – overall, by gender, and by type of product.

№	Product/food type	People with intolerance to individual products		Gender distribution				Comparison by gender p < 0.01		P
		Total		Men		Women		χ^2	LR	
		Number	% of surveyed individuals	Number	% of surveyed individuals	Number	% of surveyed individuals			
1.	Oats	576	34.3	124	7.3	452	26.9			
2.	Wheat	1 465	92.8	337	20.0	1128	67.1	10.64	11.26	0.002
3.	Rice	693	43.9	183	10.8	510	30.3			
4.	Corn	1 104	69.9	239	14.2	865	51.5			
5.	Rye	1 009	63.9	239	14.2	770	45.8			
6.	Grain /paste/	861	54.5	217	27.1	644	38.3			
7.	Gluten	650	41.2	153	9.1	497	29.6			
8.	Almonds	564	35.7	139	8.2	425	25.3			
9.	Brazil nuts	386	24.4	105	6.2	281	16.7			
10.	Cashew	630	39.9	161	9.5	469	27.9			
11.	Tea	12	0.8	3	0.1	9	0.5			
12.	Walnuts	119	7.5	28	1.6	91	5.4			
13.	Milk	816	51.7	192	11.4	624	37.1			
14.	Eggs	1079	68.3	256	15.2	823	49.0			
15.	Chicken meat	25	1.6	5	0.2	20	1.9			
16.	Lamb meat	22	1.4	3	0.1	19	1.1			
17.	Veal meat	14	0.9	2	0.1	12	0.7			
18.	Pork meat	37	2.3	5	0.2	32	1.9			
19.	White fish – cod, flounder	196	12.4	45	2.6	151	8.9			
20.	Freshwater fish – mix	102	6.5	23	1.3	79	4.7			
21.	Tuna	36	2.3	3	0.1	33	1.9			
22.	Shellfish – shrimps, crabs, lobsters, mussels	402	25.5	100	5.9	302	17.9			
23.	Broccoli	8	0.5	4	0.2	4	0.2			
24.	White cabbage	58	3.7	15	0.8	43	2.5			
25.	Carrots	194	12.3	45	2.6	149	8.8			
26.	Leek	103	6.5	33	1.9	70	4.1	4.98	3.35	0.02
27.	Potatoes	299	18.9	79	4.7	220	13.1			
28.	Celery	225	14.2	59	3.5	166	9.8			
29.	Cucumber	5	0.3	1	0.01	4	0.2			
30.	Peppers – red, green, yellow	355	22.5	91	5.4	264	15.7			
31.	Beans – peas, lentils, beans	497	31.5	131	7.8	366	21.7			
32.	Grapefruit	59	3.7	14	0.8	45	2.6			
33.	Melon and watermelon	16	1.0	5	0.2	11	0.6			
34.	Peanuts	551	34.9	138	8.2	413	24.5			
35.	Soya	381	24.1	82	4.8	299	17.8			
36.	Cocoa	187	11.8	38	2.2	149	8.8	7.10	11.14	0.004
37.	Apple	8	0.5	1	0.01	7	0.4			
38.	Currant	18	1.1	3	0.1	15	0.8			
39.	Olives	12	0.8	2	0.1	10	0.5			
40.	Oranges and lemons	207	13.1	65	3.8	142	8.4			
41.	Strawberries	136	8.7	26	1.5	110	6.5			
42.	Tomatoes	184	11.7	49	2.9	135	8.0			
43.	Ginger	58	3.7	16	0.9	42	2.5			
44.	Garlic	32	2.0	9	0.5	23	1.3			
45.	Mushroom	164	10.4	38	2.2	126	7.5	4.63	3.23	0.03
46.	Yeast	964	61.1	224	13.3	740	44.0			

Note: Some individuals have intolerances to more than 1 product; therefore, the sum of the number of individuals with food intolerances by product may be greater than the total number of individuals studied (1679 individuals).

Table 3. Distribution of food intolerances in the studied individuals by degree of manifestation.

		No intolerance		Degree of manifestation of food intolerance					
		Number	%	Light degree		Medium degree		Heavy degree	
				Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
1.	Oats	1003	63.5	508	32.2	60	3.8	8	0.5
2.	Wheat	114	7.2	855	54.1	490	31.0	120	7.6
3.	Rice	886	56.1	630	39.9	52	3.3	11	0.7
4.	Corn	475	30.1	811	51.4	237	15.0	56	3.5
5.	Rye	570	36.1	859	54.4	124	7.9	26	1.6
6.	Grain / paste, c	718	45.5	721	45.7	113	7.2	27	1.7
7.	Gluten	929	58.8	483	30.6	128	8.1	39	2.5
8.	Almonds	1015	64.3	474	30.0	66	4.2	24	1.5
9.	Brazil nuts	1193	75.3	319	20.2	39	2.5	28	1.8
10.	Cashew	949	60.1	484	30.7	94	6.0	52	3.3
11.	Tea	1567	99.2	12	0.8	–	–	–	–
12.	Walnuts	1460	92.5	105	6.6	5	0.3	9	0.6
13.	Milk	763	48.3	461	29.1	217	13.7	138	8.7
14.	Eggs	500	31.7	540	34.2	362	22.9	177	11.2
15.	Chicken meat	1554	98.4	22	1.4	3	0.2	–	–
16.	Lamb meat	1557	98.6	22	1.4	–	–	–	–
17.	Veal meat	1565	99.1	14	0.9	–	–	–	–
18.	Pork meat	1542	97.7	35	2.2	2	0.1	–	–
19.	White fish – cod, flounder	1383	87.6	181	11.5	15	0.9	–	–
20.	Freshwater fish – mix	1477	93.5	99	6.3	3	0.2	–	–
21.	Tuna	1543	97.7	34	2.2	2	0.1	–	–
22.	Shellfish – shrimps, crabs, lobsters, mussels	1177	74.5	352	22.3	41	2.6	9	0.6
23.	Broccoli	1571	99.5	8	0.5	–	–	–	–
24.	White cabbage	1521	96.3	57	3.6	1	0.1	–	–
25.	Carrots	1358	87.7	192	12.2	2	0.1	–	–
26.	Leek	1476	93.5	102	6.5	1	0.1	–	–
27.	Potatoes	1280	81.1	290	18.4	8	0.5	1	0.1
28.	Celery	1354	85.8	214	13.6	8	0.5	3	0.2
29.	Cucumber	1574	99.7	5	0.3	–	–	–	–
30.	Peppers – red, green, yellow	1224	77.5	304	19.3	41	2.6	10	0.6
31.	Beans – peas, lentils, beans	1082	68.5	460	29.1	32	2.0	5	0.3
32.	Grapefruit	1520	96.3	57	3.6	2	0.1	–	–
33.	Melon and watermelon	1563	99.0	15	0.9	1	0.01	–	–
34.	Peanuts	1028	65.1	489	31.0	46	2.9	16	1.0
35.	Soya	1198	75.9	364	23.1	15	0.9	2	0.1
36.	Cocoa	1392	88.2	184	11.7	2	0.1	1	0.1
37.	Apple	1571	99.5	8	0.5	–	–	–	–
38.	Currant	1561	98.9	18	1.1	–	–	–	–
39.	Olives	1567	99.2	10	0.6	2	0.1	–	–
40.	Oranges and lemons	1372	86.9	203	12.9	4	0.3	–	–
41.	Strawberries	1442	91.3	135	8.5	2	0.1	–	–
42.	Tomatoes	1395	88.3	183	11.6	1	0.1	–	–
43.	Ginger	1521	96.3	57	3.6	1	0.1	–	–
44.	Garlic	1547	98.0	32	2.0	–	–	–	–
45.	Mushroom	1415	89.6	150	9.5	6	0.4	8	0.5
46.	Yeast	615	38.9	684	43.3	204	12.9	76	4.8

tential is weaker for Brazil nuts (1.8%), wheat (1.7%), rye flour (1.6%), and almonds (1.5%). For the remaining products studied, strong manifestations of intolerance are very rare, below 1%. For 15 of the products studied, no “heavy” degree of manifestation of intolerance was registered (chicken and pork, white fish, freshwater fish mix and tuna, white cabbage, carrots, leeks, grapefruit, melon/watermelon, olives, oranges/lemons, strawberries, tomatoes, and ginger).

The largest part of the products shows the potential for a “medium” degree of intolerance. This occurs most often with wheat – 33.0%; eggs – 22.9%; followed by corn – 15.0%; milk – 13.7%; and yeast – 12.9%. About 8% fall on rye flour, grain, and gluten; cashews – 6.0%; about 4% each for oats and almonds; and about 3% for rice, peanuts, shellfish, and peppers. For the remaining products studied, the average degree of intolerance is very rare, below

1%. For 8 of the products, no “medium” degree of food intolerance has been established (tea, lamb and beef, broccoli, cucumber, apples, blueberries, and garlic). For the same products, there is no “strong” degree of intolerance; i.e., for them only a “light” degree of intolerance has been established.

In general, the relative share of the “light” degree of manifestation in food intolerances is the largest, and as mentioned above, there are products that show intolerance only to such a degree.

An analysis of the relationship between gender and the degree of manifestation of food intolerances in the studied foods was performed. No statistically significant gender differences were found in terms of the declared degree of manifestation of food intolerances. The frequency distribution and the relative share of individuals in the individual degrees of food intolerance (weak, moderate, severe) do not differ significantly in men and women. The data show that gender does not affect the degree to which food intolerances can manifest.

Reliable correlation dependencies between food intolerances

Table 4 presents the established reliable correlations between intolerances to different foods (statistical reliability with **chi-square tests** and **likelihood ratio**).

The data from Table 4 show significant correlations established for 20 pairs of foods, where the presence of intolerance to one of the foods indicates to varying degrees the

probability of the occurrence or presence of intolerance to the other food.

There is an extremely high degree of correlation between simultaneous intolerance to **tomatoes and soy** ($\chi^2 = 149.056$, $p = 0.00$), **peppers and legumes** ($\chi^2 = 140.323$, $p = 0.00$), and **tomatoes and legumes** ($\chi^2 = 113.507$, $p = 0.00$). The correlation is very high in the case of intolerance to **soy and peppers** ($\chi^2 = 82.174$, $p = 0.00$), **soy and mushrooms** ($\chi^2 = 49.977$, $p = 0.00$), **legumes and mushrooms** ($\chi^2 = 46.470$, $p = 0.00$), and a high degree of correlation—respectively, **eggs and peppers** ($\chi^2 = 30.209$, $p = 0.00$), **eggs and mushrooms** ($\chi^2 = 28.172$, $p = 0.00$), and **eggs and tomatoes** ($\chi^2 = 27.789$, $p = 0.00$).

The remaining reliable correlations between pairs of food intolerances are within the average range – **pork and ginger** ($\chi^2 = 9.986$, $p = 0.002$); **pork and walnuts** ($\chi^2 = 9.134$, $p = 0.003$); low – **chicken with white cabbage and peanuts**; and **pork and legumes** ($\chi^2 = 5.182$ – 5.759 , $p = 0.02$ – 0.01). The lowest correlation is for **pork and tuna** ($\chi^2 = 4.808$, $p = 0.028$) and **pork and tomatoes** ($\chi^2 = 4.169$, $p = 0.041$).

Discussion

Food intolerance is very often associated with the release and effects of mediators such as histamine and serotonin, purines, and nitrites, most often found in legumes and nuts, meat, cheese, sausages, and fish, especially if they are not properly refrigerated (Shulpekova 2021). Intolerances to fish and shellfish (seafood) are associated with different

Table 4. Reliable relationships (correlations) between the studied food intolerances.

№	Correlations between food intolerances		Pearson Chi-Square		Likelihood Ratio		Fisher's Exact Test
			Value	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Value	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)
1.	Pork	Gluten	6.186	0.013	6.099	0.014	0.023
2.		Walnuts	9.134	0.003	9.084	0.003	0.004
3.		Tuna	4.808	0.028	5.779	0.016	0.057
4.		Pulses	5.182	0.023	5.211	0.022	0.027
5.		Tomatoes	4.169	0.041	4.115	0.043	0.052
6.		Ginger	9.986	0.002		0.001	0.003
7.	Chicken	White cabbage	5.271	0.022	8.409	0.004	0.031
8.		Walnuts	5.759	0.016	5.772	0.016	0.026
9.	Milk	Tomatoes	16.540	0.000	16.837	0.000	0.000
10.		Mushroom	13.486	0.000	13.716	0.000	0.000
11.	Eggs	Peppers	30.209	0.000	32.196	0.000	0.000
12.		Tomatoes	27.789	0.000	31.394	0.000	0.000
13.		Mushroom	28.172	0.000	32.330	0.000	0.000
14.	Legumes	Peppers	140.323	0.000	132.592	0.000	0.000
15.		Tomatoes	113.507	0.000	104.493	0.000	0.000
16.		Mushroom	46.470	0.000	43.131	0.000	0.000
17.	Soy	Peppers	82.174	0.000	75.683	0.000	0.000
18.		Tomatoes	149.056	0.000	127.022	0.000	0.000
19.		Mushroom	49.977	0.000	43.488	0.000	0.000
20.	Gluten	Peppers	15.496	0.000	15.823	0.000	0.000

Asymp. Sig. (2-sided) – Asymptotic 2-sided significance in crosstabs chi-square statistic: The “2-sided” refers to the alternative hypothesis tested, which is that the distribution of cases in the crosstab can either be positively associated (as X increases, Y increases) or negatively associated (as X increases, Y decreases), vs. the null hypothesis of no association. The chi-square test indeed does use only one tail of the distribution.

Exact Sig. (2-sided) – Exact Tests™ is a statistical package in SPSS for analyzing continuous or categorical data by *exact* methods. This value represents the 2-tailed p-value of the test. If this value is less than the significance level (common choices are 0.05 or 0.01), then the null hypothesis of the test can be rejected.

reactions of the body to specific proteins found in certain marine animals, with the most problematic foods in this category being shrimp, crab, lobster, squid, oysters, mussels, and others (Dannaeus and Inganäs 1981). Symptoms of intolerance can also be provoked by the intake of various food additives (Turner and Kemp 2012), such as dyes (erythrosine), preservatives (nitrites), emulsifiers, enzymes, etc., and these intolerances are dose-dependent – the more consumed, the more violent the reaction.

IgG-mediated food intolerance is thought to be associated with increased intestinal permeability, allowing nutrients to gain access to the bloodstream and induce specific IgG production (Priedite et al. 2014), which, combined with decreased production of anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-10 and TGFβ1, is implicated in irritable bowel syndrome (Sentsova et al. 2014).

Vojdani (2009) studies a comparison between food antigens of raw and processed foods; IgE antibodies showed a 3–8-fold increase against processed food antigens in 31% of the patients. Almost every tested serum with high levels of antibodies against modified food antigens showed very high levels of antibodies against myelin basic protein, oxidized low-density lipoprotein, AGE-human serum albumin, and AGE-hemoglobin. Antibodies against modified food antigens, by reacting with AGEs and tissue proteins, may cause perturbation in degenerative and autoimmune diseases such as diabetes, atherosclerosis, inflammation, autoimmunity, neurodegeneration, and neuroautoimmunity (Vojdani 2009).

IgG-mediated food intolerance has been associated with a wide range of specific and nonspecific symptoms: allergy-related symptoms (increased irritability, rashes, urticaria, and asthma) (Schafer et al. 2001; Vance et al. 2004; Collard 2010; Antico et al. 2011; Gaur and Kumar 2013), neurological manifestations such as migraine or migraine-like headache, drowsiness after eating, lethargy, and a general feeling of unwellness (Rees 2005; Arroyave Hernandez et al. 2007; Mitchell et al. 2011; Aydinlar et al. 2013; Pizza 2013), and increased irritability. Gastrointestinal symptoms suggestive of irritable bowel syndrome (Guo et al. 2012; Sentsova et al. 2014; Jansen et al. 2016), bloating, a feeling of heaviness in the stomach, diarrhea, constipation, heartburn, vomiting, muscle and joint pain, and food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome are examples of severe non-IgE immune-mediated food reactions that are part of a spectrum of what is believed to be T-cell-mediated (Halbrich 2014), as well as others, alone or in combination with several symptoms (Beyer and Teuber 2005; Collard 2010; Priedite et al. 2014).

Non-immunological adverse reactions to foods can occur after more hours, even days, compared to food allergies, and are divided into independent and dependent on host factors (Colella and Salvador Parisi 2023). Foods may contain chemicals with pharmacological activity and be present naturally, such as vasoactive amines (histamine) and salicylates, or added for preservation or to improve appearance or flavor (monosodium glutamate, tartrazine, sulfites, and benzoates). In some cases, these types of reactions may be like hypersensitivity reactions. Concomitant

alcohol consumption may worsen symptoms by inhibiting histamine breakdown and increasing intestinal permeability. In patients diagnosed with non-immunological adverse reactions to foods, it is important to rule out some psychological problems: aversions or eating disorders.

Stopping the consumption of the “intolerable” food in most cases leads to a significant improvement in the assessment of symptoms (Hernandez et al. 2007; Wilders-Truschning et al. 2008; Guo et al. 2012; Kumar et al. 2013). Important is the fact that in food-intolerant people, it is possible to detect allergic symptoms and IgG antibodies to certain foods instead of the food-specific IgE antibodies (Shakoor et al. 2016). This sometimes makes nutritional intolerances and food allergies difficult for differential diagnosis (Beyer and Teuber 2005; Collard 2010).

The high prevalence of food intolerances to *cereals* can be linked to the high consumption of such products in Bulgaria. It is also important to note the existence of “artificial gluten” in ketchup and various sauces, in ice cream and sweets, in chips and French fries, frozen vegetables, ready-made broths, and others as a stabilizer and mixer, as well as in lipsticks and powders, which are labeled “modified food starch or deoxidized non-vegetable protein.” The use of such foods, additives, and cosmetics can cause gastrointestinal symptoms and make differential diagnosis with food intolerance difficult (Beyer and Teuber 2005; Turner and Kemp 2012).

Milk intolerance and improper absorption of lactose in the small intestine lead to its fermentation with gas, diarrhea, and abdominal pain. Approximately 75% of the adult population worldwide shows a decrease in enzyme activity, and lactose-intolerant people often have genetic hypolactasia (an autosomal recessive condition resulting from a physiologically determined decrease in lactase production). *Egg intolerance* is most often limited to the digestive system and is rarely life-threatening (unlike egg allergy) and is associated with difficulty digesting egg white, yolk, or both. This intolerance can develop at any age, last for several years, or remain lifelong (Halbrich et al. 2014).

Vegetables, fruits, and meat are among the least likely to cause food intolerance in the subjects studied. In case of deficiency of the enzyme fructase, a similar clinical picture develops after consuming foods containing sugar and fructose, which is why many people experience abdominal pain and bloating, accompanied by diarrhea, after consuming sweet fruits and jams, juices, or sweets. The intake of fruit juices, especially in childhood, can cause complaints due to intolerance to sugar alcohols (sorbitol, maltitol, etc.). This is most often observed when consuming pear and grape juice. The content of phenylethylamine in chocolate, mature cheese, and red wine can cause migraine headaches in people with intolerance. Other vasoactive amines, such as tyramine and histamine, contained mainly in strawberries, tomatoes, sea fish, pineapple, peanuts, etc., can cause urticaria, headache, and a drop in blood pressure.

The results of the present study show that food intolerances are found more often in women than in men, similar to other studies (Shakoor et al. 2016; Harish Babu et al. 2008), but there is also data showing that there are no

gender differences in terms of IgG-mediated food intolerance (Chang et al. 2013). The results also revealed that females are more likely to have “leaky guts,” predisposing them to the development of food intolerance, than males. In the present study, significant gender differences (with a predominance of the female sex) were found only for wheat, leek, cocoa, and mushrooms.

The established correlations between the individual types of food intolerances indicate the probability of cross-intolerances and the potentially most common foods causing them. Combined intolerance to different types of foods is primarily associated with the presence of the same or similar immunological characteristics in them.

The leader in cross-intolerances is **pork** (participating in 6 cross-pairs – with gluten, nuts, tuna, legumes (pulses), tomatoes, and ginger), which is most often associated with cross-reactivity to serum albumins of the corresponding food products, as well as with the content of biologically active substances in meat, such as histamine, serotonin, nitrites, etc. (Dannaeus and Inganäs 1981).

Tomatoes are among the very frequently and widely used products that participate in 5 cross-intolerance pairs. The content of acids, alkaloids (solanine), lycopene, oxalates, histamine, pesticide residues, etc. creates conditions for individual and/or combined manifestations of intolerance, as well as irritation of the gastrointestinal tract, acid reflux, “irritable bowel syndrome,” joint pain (due to accumulation of solanine), kidney and urination problems, lycopentodermia (accumulation of lycopene), etc. (Halbrich 2014).

Legumes (peas, lentils, beans, etc.), containing various proteins, purines, phytic acid, etc., mushrooms, and peppers (participating in 4 pairs of cross-food intolerances) also show the presence of the same or similar immunological characteristics. The combination of several intolerances creates significant difficulties in the diet and lifestyle of affected individuals (Zeng et al. 2013), and differences in cultural and dietary habits in different parts of the world are contributing to variations in the global prevalence rates of food-specific IgG antibodies.

Authors recommend studying the prevalence of food-specific IgG antibodies in an otherwise asymptomatic population in order to establish local reference ranges for different food intolerances (Shakoor et al. 2016). The great preventive importance of this approach is taken into account – the identification of food intolerances in individuals makes it possible to adjust the diet and eating habits, eliminate “intolerable” foods or additives, and replace them with others. Food intolerances are of great importance in cases of increased body weight and obesity, metabolic disorders, eating disorders, chronic diseases, and difficulties with weight normalization and improvement of health status.

Conclusion

The present study also responds to the need to establish specific features of the Bulgarian population in the spread

of food intolerances and the correlations between them, contributing to the optimization of dietary regimens at the individual level, prescribing healthy individual diets, and maintaining the health of the individual. The results of the study can be used in the treatment of nutritional diseases, creating an appropriate individual diet, or as an indication for restrictions in the use of certain food groups, products, or food supplements. Very important are the data on existing intolerances to major food groups in conditions with impaired metabolism, excess body weight, and other eating disorders (impairments), in which the correct diet is a key factor in the treatment and prevention of the condition.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

M. Nikolova had a great contribution in developing the research methodology, collecting data from the subjects, critical review and overall drafting of the manuscript, A. Alakidi made significant contributions to preparing the literature review, drafting the reference list of cited authors, reviewing the manuscript for style and language, V. Petkova and Milen Dimitrov reviewed and revised the manuscript for important intellectual content and compliance with the journal requirements as well as the language, A. Agovska took a leading part in developing and analyzing the data, statistical evaluation and drafting the manuscript.

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Data availability

All data that support the findings reported in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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